

**PREVALENCE OF MALARIA IN GWAKO; A CASE STUDY OF INDIVIDUALS
ATTENDING JOEFAG HOSPITAL GWAKO GWAGWALADA, ABUJA.**

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ABSTRACT

Malaria is a major public health concern in Nigeria, with significant morbidity and mortality rates. This study aims to determine the prevalence of malaria among individuals attending Joefag hospital in Gwako Gwagwalada, Abuja. A cross-sectional study design was employed, and data was collected using laboratory tests. A total of 300 residence within the range of 1-75 years were sampled for malaria parasite using Rapid Diagnostics Test {RDTs}. A finger prick was used to collect the sample The resulted provided a valuable insight into the burden of malaria in the Gwako community and informed public health interventions. A total of 300 patients with clinical suspicion of malaria comprising of 101 males and 119 females were examined. Rapid diagnostic tests were used to detect the presence of plasmodium falciparum a species that cause malaria parasites in the samples. The data generated from this study were presented using descriptive statistics. The results were analyzed in percentage. And the finding of this study will contribute to the understanding of malaria epidemiology in the region and guide efforts to reduce its burden. From the study conducted A total of three hundred (300) patients' samples were examined for

malaria using RDTs kits. Out of the numbers, 107(35.7%) had malaria parasite. Among the age groups, 1 – 15 years had the highest malaria prevalence rate of 38(33.3%) while 61-75 years had the least malaria prevalence rate of 14(12.3%). While 16 – 30 years had the second highest malaria prevalence rate of 29(25.4%). The result of this study revealed that malaria is prevalent among the 1-15 years. There is need to ensure that mothers protect their children from mosquito bite by ensuring that they sleep under ITN.

Key words; Malaria, plasmodium species, (RDTs Rapid Diagnostic Tests), Prevalence.

Introduction

Malaria has played an important role in the history of mankind because it is a constant threat to human health and it affects economic development and growth in areas highly affected by the disease. The disease is more lethal in children 0-5years, pregnant women and in people from non-malaria endemic areas. An estimated 247 million cases, nearly a million deaths, mostly in children less than five years old were attributed to malaria (WHO, 2018a).

Nigeria accounts for a quarter of all malaria cases in the World Health Organization's (WHO) African Region and transmission occurs all-year round in the Southern States of the country (WHO, 2018a). In Nigeria, malaria is directly responsible for over one million deaths of children below school age and one quarter of an average family income is spent on the treatment of malaria (Etuk and Umoh, 2021). Despite the attempts to eradicate malaria in Africa between 1955-1978, the disease resurged during the 1980s and 90s alongside with rapid spread of resistance to mainstay antimalarial medicines, for example, chloroquine and sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine (Bjorkman and Bhattarai 2020). However, the advent of a new millennium has been accompanied by increased awareness and expressed commitment by political leaders in Africa and by the international community to Roll Back Malaria.

This has been clearly outlined in the Millennium Development Goals, the Abuja Declaration and in the Global Malaria Action Plan (WHO, 2020a; WHO, 2018b). This new era has coincided with access to powerful tools to control the disease, for example, efficacious combination treatment based on artemisinin-derivatives as well as improved vector control with long lasting insecticides treated nets and a revival of indoor residual spraying. Integrated, wide scale, high coverage interventions with these tools have recently shown 2 persuasive evidences of marked reduction in overall child mortality and burden of disease in endemic areas of Africa (Bhattarai et al., 2017). Malaria is one of the World's most deadly and life-threatening parasitic disease (Abah and Temple, 2018) and Dougnon et al; 2019 described as one of the World's deadliest diseases affecting people, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions of the World. Malaria parasitaemia is the presence of malaria parasite in the red blood cells causing feverish condition, anaemia and in many cases especially in children resulting to death. It is typically caused by single-celled obligate protozoan parasite of the genus Plasmodium (Udoh et al., 2017) and the species are: falciparum, malariae, oval, vivax and those mostly found in Sub-Saharan African are falciparum and malariae species (Idowu et al., 2019, Okonko et al., 2018, Tela et al., 2019, Unata et al., 2018, Pamela et al., 2017). Nevertheless, Idowu et al., 2010, Pamela et al., 2015 reported that the majority of malaria infections in Sub-Saharan Africa are caused by Plasmodium falciparum, more so, the main causes of morbidity and mortality affecting people of all age groups especially children in endemic areas such as Nigeria (Olasehinde et al., 2018).

In areas where it is endemic such as Nigeria, it poses a major problem to both human capital and economic development among other factors (Nwanosike et al., 2019). Moreover, it has been estimated to cause death of two million children globally per annum (Okafor and Oke-Oso, 2019). Globally, nearly 50% of the world's 3.28% to 3.40% billion people live in areas at risk of malaria

infections (Tyndall et al., 2018, Orok et al.,2016), which are distributed in 106 nations (Nigeria Fact Sheet, 2018). Okonko et al., 2018, reported that 300 to 500 million clinical cases occur globally leading to over 1 million deaths. The world Health Organization estimated that 216 million of malaria cases occurred in 2019, of which 81% occurred in Africa (Nigeria Malaria Fact Sheet, 2081), in the African region, 30 nations accounted for 90% of global malaria deaths and are found in Sub-Saharan Africa. Typically, Nigeria, Democratic Republic of Cong, Tanzania, Uganda, Mozambique and Cote d'ivore account for approximately 103 million malaria cases and 47% of the world total per annum (Orok et al.,2016). In a country like Nigeria where malaria is endemic, malaria is common to children, young, even the elderly and represents a substantial public health challenge (Okoroiwu et al., 2018).

The most critical factors incriminated in the spread or eradication of malarial disease include human behaviors (shifting population centers; changing farming methods); living standards and poverty as the predisposing factors associated with the disease (Worrall et al.,2023). The availability of numerous breeding places for malaria parasite vectors (Mosquitoes), the incessant rainfall, unsanitary environmental conditions, ignorance, poor behavioral attitudes and inadequately planned socio-economic projects have made the Nigerian environment a fertile ground for the escalation of the malaria infection (Anthonio-Nkonjio et al.,2018; Okoroiwu et al.,2018). Likewise, it has been observed that there is high level of malaria infection in Abuja, the capital City of Nigeria (Okoroiwu, 2019). The reason is due to the tropical nature of Abuja coupled with lifestyles and behaviors, micro-climate, topography, population density and cultural practices among others.

The main broad objective of this study was find out the prevalence of malaria in Gwako; a case study of individuals attending Joefag hospital Gwako Gwagwalada, Abuja. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- ❖ To determine the prevalence of malaria in Gwako a case study of individuals in Gwako Gwagwalada, Abuja.
- ❖ To ascertain the overall prevalence of malaria in Gwako a case study of individuals attending Joefag hospital Gwako Gwagwalada, Abuja.
- ❖ To assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding malaria prevention and treatment among individuals attending Joefag hospital.
- ❖ To identify the factors associated with malaria prevalence in Gwako community.

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- ❖ what is the current prevalence of malaria among individuals attending Hospital Gwako, Gwagwalada Abuja?
- ❖ what are the demographic characteristics of individuals diagnosed with malaria in Gwako?
- ❖ what are the common symptoms and clinical presentations of malaria among individuals in Gwako, Gwagwalada Abuja?
- ❖ what are the current malaria strategies implemented in Gwako, Gwagwalada Abuja?
- ❖ what is the level of awareness and knowledge about malaria prevention and control measures among individuals in Gwako, Gwagwalada Abuja?

Methodology

A cross-sectional study design was deployed. And an experimental survey was used to collect data at different individuals at appoint in time.

This study was carried out in Gwako of Gwagwalada area council Abuja, Nigeria. FCT is in central Nigeria the headquarter of all the thirty-six states. Specifically, Joefag hospital was chosen for the study. Joefag hospital is located in Gwako 2 After Ecwa Church, Gwagwalada, Abuja. Gwako is located in Gwagwalada, a Local Government Area (LGA) in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Nigeria. Gwako is one of the villages within the Gwagwalada LGA. The area is predominantly rural, with a mix of residential and agricultural land use. It is situated in the northern part of the FCT and is bordered by other wards within Gwagwalada LGA.

Sample Size and Data Collection

A total number of three hundred (300) samples was collected (age ranged 1 to 75 years) consisting of one hundred and one (101) males and one hundred and ninety-nine females (199), females suspected for malaria and who had not taken antimalarial drugs and within two weeks were included. Patients with underlying disease were excluded from the study.

An experimental method was administered to the participants for data collection. The experimental method includes the following variables: socio-demographic characteristics which includes; sex, age. Laboratory testing for malaria parasites was also conducted.

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences software (SPSS) version 21. Continuous variables were summarized using mean and standard deviation while categorical variables were summarized using proportions.

Ethical Consideration

Approval was obtained from Joefag Hospital Gwako, Gwagwalada Area Council Abuja. Written informed consent was obtained from each study subject or guardian of the wards and confidentiality of the participant's results ensured throughout the research.

Results

A total of 300 patients with clinical suspicion of malaria comprising of 101 males and 119 females were examined. Rapid diagnostic tests were used to detect the presence of plasmodium falciparum a species that cause malaria parasites in the samples. The data generated from this study were presented using descriptive statistics. The results were analyzed in percentage.

The overall malaria prevalence in the research was 107 (35.7%), indicating that malaria remains a serious public health concern in the area, with *Plasmodium falciparum* being the most common species. Malaria was more common in people between the ages of 1-15 and 16-30 respectively (33.3%). Providing health education that enhances people's knowledge of the disease and changing community (ITN) Insecticide-treated nets usage behaviors may assist to stem the spread of the disease. Findings of the study reveals the following. Out of the 300 samples examined, 32 (27.4%) of the males and 85(72.6%) of the females were positive of malaria. There was much significant difference between the male and female patients infected with malaria.

The age incidence of malaria among samples of patients is shown in (Table 4.3). The participants were aged between 1 and 75 years. More participants were in the age group of 1 – 15 years and the least were in the age group of 61 – 75 years. Among the age groups, 1 – 15 years had the highest malaria prevalence rate of 38(33.3%) while 61-75 years had the least malaria prevalence rate of 14(12.3%). While 16 – 30 years had the second highest malaria prevalence rate of 29(25.4%).

In conclusion, the study shows that malaria prevalence rate (35.7%) is high in Joefag Hospital Gwako Gwagwalada Abuja.

Table 1 Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Status	Frequency	Percentage %
Single	120	40

Married	111	37
Separated	32	10.7
Cohabiting	4	1.3
widow	33	11
Total	300	100
Level	Frequency	Percentage%
No education	16	5.3
primary	75	25
secondary	120	40
Tertiary	89	29.7

On marital status, of the respondents 37% were married while those who were single was 40%, separated were 10.7%, 11% were widows and only a small proportion 1.3% were cohabiting as shown in Table 1.

Table 2. Overall Prevalence of Malaria using (RDTs) among patients attending Jeofag Hospital Gwako.

Illness	No. Examined	No. Infected (F)	Percentage %
Malaria	300	107	35.7%
Total	300	107	

Researcher's field work 2024

From the table above, A total of three hundred (300) patients' samples were examined for malaria using RDTs kits. Out of the numbers, 107 (35.7%) had malaria parasite.

Table 3. Characteristics and Distribution of Malaria using (RDTs) among sex-related.

Sex	No Tested	No Infected (F)	Percentage %
Male	101	32	27
Female	199	85	73
Total	300	117	100

Researcher's field work 2024

Pie chart showing the Distribution of Malaria using (RDTs) among sex-related.

The prevalence of malaria between genders is shown in Table 3. Out of the 300 samples examined, 32 (27%) of the males and 85(73%) of the females were positive of malaria. There was much significant difference between the male and female patients infected with malaria.

Table.4 Characteristics of Malaria Among Samples tested according to age group.

Age Group	No; Tested	No; Infected (F)	Percentage %
1-15	79	38	33.3
16-30	68	29	25.4
31-45	55	16	14.0

46-60	51	17	15
61-75	47	14	12.3
TOTAL	300	114	100

Researcher's field work 2024

The age incidence of malaria among samples of patients shown in (Table 4). The participants were aged between 1 and 75 years. More participants were in the age group of 1 – 15 years and the least were in the age group of 61 – 75 years. Among the age groups, 1 – 15 years had the highest malaria prevalence rate of 38(33.3%) while 61-75 years had the least malaria prevalence rate of 14(12.3%). While 16 – 30 years had the second highest malaria prevalence rate of 29(25.4%).

Discussion

Plasmodium falciparum, which infects most individuals, is the primary cause of malaria, which is a major cause of feverish illness in children in Africa. Children under the age of five are more at risk. The Integrated Management of pediatric disease (IMCI) plan, which attempts to enhance family and community practices in the management of pediatric disease, includes malaria as a febrile sickness (Goves, 1997). According to WHO (2009), malaria is the leading cause of death in young children and has a high prevalence in this age group.

In this study Malaria was more common in people between the ages of 1-15 and 16-30 respectively (33.3%). Providing health education that enhances people's knowledge of the disease and changing community (ITN) Insecticide-treated nets usage behaviors may assist to stem the spread of the disease. In comparison, Ejezie and Ezedinachi (1992) found a malaria prevalence of 44.8% in children under the age of 12 in Calabar, South South, Nigeria, and 32.9% in children aged 1 to 14 in Kano State (Adeleke, 2007). Given conflicting reports regarding the prevalence and contagiousness of malaria in African children, a comparative evaluation of the findings from this study will empirically highlight the present patterns. Compared to the typical projections of 300–500 million cases (WHO, 2000), the WHO Malaria report (WHO, 2008a) projected 247 million cases of malaria.

According to the most recent WHO Malaria report (WHO, 2019), there are approximately 243 million cases of malaria worldwide. The widespread use of malaria therapies including LLINs, ACTs, and IRS was credited with the observed decreases in malaria cases (WHO, 2019).

In this study more participants were in the age group of 1 – 15 years and the least were in the age group of 61 – 75 years. Among the age groups, 1 – 15 years had the highest malaria prevalence rate of 38(33.3%) while 61-75 years had the least malaria prevalence rate of 14(12.3%). While 16 – 30 years had the second highest malaria prevalence rate of 29(25.4%).

This study is supported by reports of a decrease in the prevalence of malaria in various regions of sub-Saharan Africa (Bouyou-Akotet et al., 2019; Delacollette et al., 2019). Following the IMCI guidelines for the assumed treatment strategy is likely to result in more overtreatment and, unavoidably, a failure to address other fever sources. In fact, research on critically ill patients receiving treatment for "malaria" revealed that the mortality rate was much higher for those with a negative slide than for those with a positive one (Reyburn et al., 2020).

There have been more and more calls to improve malaria diagnosis and case management since the nearly universal adoption of ACT. According to the new WHO guidelines, a laboratory test should be conducted prior to treatment in order to treat patients effectively, guarantee the sustainability of ACT, and preserve the "useful lifespan" of ACTs (WHO, 2010). Consequently, initiatives to increase access to parasitological diagnostics ought to be undertaken. Currently, there are two options: expanding the capacity to perform microscopy or using RDTs widely, which, unlike microscopy, don't require any special skills and can be done without electricity.

Conclusions

Malaria is a major public health problem in tropical and subtropical countries caused by very different organisms, protozoa, respectively, and transmitted via different mechanisms. People in endemic areas are at a risk of contracting infections concurrently. There is a considerable overlap of signs and symptoms of malaria. The overall malaria prevalence in the research was 107 (35.7%), indicating that malaria remains a serious public health concern in the area, with *Plasmodium falciparum* being the most common species. Malaria was more common in people between the ages of 1-15 and 16-30 respectively (33.3%). Providing health education that enhances people's

knowledge of the disease and changing community (ITN) Insecticide-treated nets usage behaviors may assist to stem the spread of the disease. Findings of the study reveals the following. Out of the 300 samples examined, 32 (27.4%) of the males and 85(72.6%) of the females were positive of malaria. There was much significant difference between the male and female patients infected with malaria.

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In conclusion, the study shows that malaria prevalence rate (35.7%) is high in Joefag Hospital Gwako Gwagwalada Abuja.

Limitation of the study

- **Financial constraint**– Insufficient fund will in general block the proficiency of the specialist in obtaining for the important materials, writing or data and during the time spent information assortment (web, survey and interview).
- **Time constraint**– The researcher will all the while participate in this review with other scholarly work. This thus will eliminate the time committed for the exploration work.

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